

THE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Today’s professional language teacher is well-versed in diverse techniques and new approaches, as well as the history and evolution of teaching strategies. In reality, the modern teacher will employ a range of methodologies and approaches, selecting techniques from each method that they believe are beneficial and using them in accordance with the learning environment and objectives.

Key words: Method, teacher, teaching, foreign, language, listening, writing.

They prepare their lessons to facilitate the understanding of the new language being taught and do not rely on one specific «best method». There are some examples of it: The teacher proposes a variety of exercises, both written and oral, to improve the learner’s accuracy, fluency and communicative ability. The teacher corrects errors immediately if the scope of the classroom activity is accuracy, but if the scope of the activity is fluency these errors will be corrected later on. The teacher develops all four linguistic capabilities (reading, writing, listening and speaking). To improve pronunciation the teacher uses drills, where students repeat automatically the phrases spoken by the teacher. The teacher helps the student personalize the use of grammatical and lexical elements used in class. The teacher understands that a didactic program has to include not only grammar and lexis, but also linguistic functions, colloquialisms, idioms, etc. The teacher introduces exercises of guided discovery for new grammar rules. At times the teacher may translate – but only if they know both languages very well and believe it is the most efficient way to provide the meaning of a new concept in that moment, especially for abstract ideas. The teacher is committed to developing a wide range of resources in order to give relevant, stimulating, and productive lessons. It is impossible to do everything if only one method is used. As a result, professional EFL teachers follow what is described as the Principled Eclecticism approach, where students are also encouraged to be autonomous in their learning. However, some private schools and training companies still prefer to promote a specific in-house branded method or approach, though often mainly for commercial or marketing reasons rather than for didactic reasons. Suggestopedia, This method is based on the idea that the mind has great potential and can retain information by the power of suggestion. This teaching method uses relaxation as a means of retaining new knowledge. In their initial lessons learners receive large quantities of information in the new language. The text is translated and then read aloud with classical music in the background. The scope is to supply an atmosphere of total relaxation where understanding is purely accidental and subliminal. Using large quantities of linguistic material introduces the idea that language understanding is easy and natural. In the following lesson, learners use the material in a variety of communication activities. The original learning techniques and theory developed in 1970s to 1980s

by Georgi Lozanov have since developed into the Accelerated Learning movement. This method is focused on meaningful texts and vocabulary. Total Physical Response (TPR). This method draws on the basic principles of how young children learn their first language. Developed by James Asher, this teaching method involves a wide range of physical activities and a lot of listening and comprehension, as well as an emphasis on learning as fun and stimulating. Total Physical Response has limitations, especially when teaching abstract language and tasks, but is widely considered to be effective for beginners and is still the standard approach for young learners. The Silent Way. Another example of a method categorized under the Humanistic Approaches, with this technique the teacher is supposed to be practically silent – hence the name of the method – and avoids explaining everything to the students. This method is based on a problem solving approach to learning, whereby the students’ learning becomes autonomous and co-operative. The scope is to help students select the appropriate phrases and know how to control them, with good intonation and rhythm. The teacher does not repeat the material nor supplies the phrases that the student has to imitate, and there is no use of the learner’s native language. Patterns contain vocabulary, and coloured guides for pronunciation are used to assist the teacher in guiding the students’ understanding while saying the least amount possible. Each method has a different focus or priority, so let’s look at what this means in practical terms in the classroom. The more common methods have a link to a separate page with more details and an explanation of how they work, including the most common method currently used – Communicative Language Teaching:

Method

Focus

Characteristics

Grammar Translation

Written literary texts

Translate from English into your native language

Direct Method (also called Natural Method)

Everyday spoken language

Student learns by associating meaning directly in English

Audio-Lingual Method

Sentence and sound patterns

Listening and speaking drills and pattern practice only in English

Cognitive Code Approach

Grammar rules

English grammar rules deduced and then understood in context

Humanistic Approaches – 4 popular examples:

The Silent Way

Student interaction rather than teacher

Teacher is silent to allow student awareness of how English works

Suggestopedia

Meaningful texts and vocabulary

Relaxed atmosphere, with music; encourages subliminal learning of English

Community Language Learning

Student interaction

Understanding of English through active student interaction

Method

Focus

Characteristics

Comprehension Approach (Natural Approach, the Learnables, and Total Physical Response)

Listening comprehension

English speaking delayed until students are ready; meaning clarified through actions and visuals

Communicative Language Teaching

Interaction, authentic communication and negotiating meaning

Conclusion

Understanding of English through active student interaction; role play, games, information gaps. Content-based, Task-based, and Participatory Approaches. What is being communicated, not structure of English. Content based on relevance to students' lives: topics, tasks, problem-solving. Learning Strategy Training, Cooperative Learning, and Multiple Intelligences. How to learn? Teach learning strategies, cooperation; activities vary according to different intelligences. 10 creative ways to teach English that deliver outstanding results. As a creative school, with a track record in fantastic English results, we are often asked what our specific approach is: how do we teach through the arts yet manage to maintain such high expectations from all our pupils? I'd like to share some of these approaches with you.

References

1. Xoshimova, N. (2019). External factors of associations' individuality. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 2(2), 134-136.
2. Jalolov, J. J., Makhkamova, G. T., & Ashurov, S. S. (2015). English language teaching methodology. *Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya*.
3. Isakovna, T. N. (2017). The Symbol of Mirror and its Main Poetic Functions in Fairy Tales. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 6(2), 7-11. Mamajanova, M. (2021). MODEL CONCEPT MODELING IN LINGUISTICS TYPES OF LINGUISTIC MODELS. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1), 160-163.
4. Holbekova, M., Mamajonova, M., & Holbekov, S. (2021). COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 83-85.
5. Kasimova, G. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF ICE BREAKING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 117-120.
6. Makhmudovna, K. G. (2022). Creative Strategies to Improve Vocabulary Teaching. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 259-261.
7. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2022). Developing professional communicative competence of medical students in a foreign language. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 15, 45-50.
8. Ashurali, M. (2022). HOZIRGI KUNDAGI TA'LIM TIZIMIDA ONLAYN TEXNOLOGIYALARGA ASOSLANGAN METODNI TA'LIMGA JORIY QILISHNING AKTUALLIGI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 25-28.
9. Kochkorova, Z. A. (2022). THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VERBALIZERS OF THE CONCEPT OF “WEDDING” IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(6), 250-253.
10. Ismoilova, G. (2021). FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR KLASSIFIKATSIYASI. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(2).

11. Mirzaev, A. B. U. (2022). IMPROVING EFL/ESL CLASSROOMS THROUGH USING ONLINE PLATFORMS: NEARPOD–AS AN EXAMPLE OF TOP-RATED ONLINE EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 264-270.
12. Abdumutaljonovna, P. S. (2022). Main Characteristics of Advertising Discourse in Modern Linguistics. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 9, 173-176.
13. Abdumutaljonovna, Pakirdinova Sharofat. "The function and peculiarities of advertising text in linguistics." *Confrencea 1.1 (2022)*. Oxunov, A. O. O. (2021). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA UNDOV SO'ZLAR (INTERJECTION) NING IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 401-406.
14. Gulmira, A. (2022). “QO ‘RQUV” KONSEPTI VA UNING O’RGANILISHI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 46-48. Gafurova, N. I. (2021). Structural-semantical classification of construction terms in English and Uzbek languages. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 571-575.
15. Gafurova, N. (2020). Ҳозирги замон тилшунослигида “Термин” ва унга турлича ёндашувлар. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 1(1), 58-62. Ahundjanova, M. A. (2020). METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE. *Экономика и социум*, (11), 46-49.
16. Ahundjanova, M. (2022). THE NEEDS FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS’ AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES–AS A KEY FACTOR TO BOOST LANGUAGE LEARNERS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 390-392.
17. Isaqjon, T. (2022). Strategies and techniques for improving EFL learners’ reading skills. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(11), 94-99.
18. Mirzayev, A., & Oripova, S. (2022). COMMUNICATIVE METHOD–A NEW APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 778-783.